

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LISTENING TEXTS AND LISTENING STRATEGIES

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Abstract. *Every language has a common and a natural sequence for the development of language skills. Listening skill is ranked first of all the four-folds. This highlights the importance of listening skills in the life of human beings. Learners normally face and encounter listening problems, especially in foreign languages.*

Keywords: *skills, subskills, receptive skills, productive skills.*

Language is a medium of communication, which helps the members of a community in the society, to communicate and interact with one another. This involves both verbal and non-verbal communication. Language focuses on listening and reading that can be named as passive or receptive skills while speaking and writing can be named as, active or productive skills. Listening is one of the important skills in learning a language. The process of acquiring a language starts with listening and ends up in the production of writing. After birth, a child hears a variety of sounds and can distinguish among them. Like many other subjects taught in educational places, the subject of the English language is one of the most relevant and demanded. The relevance of learning English is dictated by the needs of the modern world. Nowadays, the English language has become an international language of communication.

The President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoev pays special attention to this sphere, which has an important place in ensuring the future of the country and its development. In the Decree of President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev «On Uzbekistan's Development Strategy» is mentioned about achieving major improvement of in quality of general secondary education, facilitating the in-depth study of foreign languages, computer science, and other important and popular disciplines.

This strategy requires an overall reconsideration of the attitude to teaching and learning English as a global language through implementation of new interactive methods of teaching and ICT in education system

This paper presents arguments for an emphasis on listening comprehension in language learning/teaching. An explanation of how listeners can use strategies to enhance the learning process is presented, with a review of the existing research base on how second language listening is taught. The major part of the paper presents and discusses pedagogical recommendations.

Listening and speaking are often taught together, but beginners, especially non-literate ones, should be given more listening than speaking practice. It's important to speak as close to natural speed as possible, although with beginners some slowing is usually necessary. Without reducing speaking speed it is possible to make a language easier to comprehend by simplifying vocabulary, using shorter sentences, and increasing the number and length of pauses in speech.

Given the importance of listening in language learning and teaching it is essential for language teachers to help their young learners become effective listeners. In the communicative approach to language teaching, this means modeling listening strategies and providing listening

practice in authentic situations: those that learners are likely to encounter when they use the language outside the classroom.

The research available on second-language listening comprehension is insufficient. Comparing with other skills W. Goh said that "there are fewer insights about the process of listening and the way it is learned". Similarly, D. Richards stated that: "there is little direct research on second language listening comprehension". As for that, we are doing this research not only to help students with better listening but also to contribute a small part to enrich the listening research which has been done so far.

The most popular kind of studying English, according to the results of the survey, is listening to English songs. It is quite easy to see why: teenagers like entertainment and listening to music- that is why so many of them preferred this kind of studying to others. Moreover, something we rarely think about, but what is true and evident for teachers is the fact that listening to foreign songs can improve comprehension skills - one starts to understand the spoken language more easily.

Another suggested type of learning a foreign language is through online dictionaries or translators and here we cannot say whether this method is good or bad. Using online dictionary is helpful, especially for those who does not have the printed ones, but we would not suggest using online translators as these often give the wrong or literal translation, which does not allow a pupil or a student to learn the correct language constructions.

Next, watching films or series was offered and here it is quite the same as with the songs- one starts to understand the foreign speech better, and that is fun, too. Access to any and all types of videos is obviously a great way to improve your listening. Downloading movies and English teacher videos are all excellent. But how about using this resource in different ways? How about going onto YouTube and watching some old music videos with the lyrics coming up on the screen (subtitles) Or TED Talks! This is a very interesting and innovative resource for talks. Watching these videos not only gives you excellent access to English, but also a lot of new ideas! If you enjoy the visuals of a diary-style video, then make use of this medium because it will give you access and training to listen to more natural speech. Again, beware of bad language!

Online video classes are not very popular with the pupils who learn English, most probably because it's not that entertaining and is usually pricey. Still, we consider it to be the most effective method in terms of education, for it can give a student systematic knowledge. Its only disadvantage is that one could get bored as it is most commonly held as a lesson.

Communication in chats and messengers are good in terms of picking up new phrases of informal English, but you are less likely to learn grammar structures and even tenses using this type of practicing.

The minority of the questioned students like educational games as a way of learning English. That seems to be a good way of both entertainment and learning, but still we regard it as less effective in comparison with the other learning methods.

Listening to and reading news, articles is a great way to practice because the language of news channels and reputable organizations is clear and direct. Also, the content is always fresh and you will never get bored by reading or listening to some information that has long become old news, or is outdated. So, not only do you get to practice and improve your English, but you also stay informed.

Here are some tips for using this great resource:

- When reading an article, try reading it out loud. This is great for practicing your speaking, listening and pronunciation. As the more difficult words come along and you find yourself struggling to pronounce them, reach for your dictionary and see how the word is broken down into syllables and what the sounds are. Repeat these words out loud over and over again until they start to feel and sound natural. If you are not sure, write it down and ask someone who speaks English or your teacher to help you with the pronunciation.

- Use the different sections of news to build on your vocabulary for specific things. For example, sports news, sports articles and sports bulletins are a great way to build up vocabulary and knowledge of use of English in sport-talk. Or, watch weather reports in English and learn vocabulary for weather. This is also a great way to listen to the use of tenses as they make future predictions for weather patterns.

- Always read the comics! Comics can be difficult to understand because they can make use of irony and/or sarcasm in language, or they may be very particular to a social or cultural context for that news channel/article. But, never miss a chance to try and understand it. It doesn't take that much time to read a comic.

There are so many interesting bloggers out there today. There is something for everyone and certainly a person or group who shares many of the same sentiments and experiences as you. You can search Google for bloggers on any topic and start following them. For example, if you are into sport, then try football bloggers or basketball bloggers! One of the best things about good bloggers that manage to attract many followers is that their writing will generally be good. But, always remember that just because someone blogs in English a lot, it does not mean they are the authority on English writing and grammar. And be careful of slang and swear words! A more formal way to ensure you are following blogs that are probably written by someone who is qualified in their writing or has some experience, is following blogs of many of your favourite brands. Despite the above-mentioned advantages of using audio resources in learning English, there are some drawbacks as well.

First of all, one has to double-check the information they get in the Internet as it is not always reliable. It is hard to differentiate whether the given facts are true, or if they are just fiction.

What is more, it is practically impossible for a pupil or a student to form a plan for studying in the Internet that will include all the necessary forms of any learning process and will logically lead him or her to getting systematic knowledge. We consider this drawback to be the main disadvantage of learning through the Internet in case if this is the only one way of studying of a foreign language.

From our point of view, the role of a real, professional teacher, who can arrange the correct process of learning, change it according to the needs of a certain pupil or a student remains great.

Still, we think that if used wisely, the listening resources are highly beneficial for students of all ages due to the fact that they are within the easy reach for almost anyone and are simple in use.

In recent years, the issue of the use of new information technologies in school has been increasingly raised. This is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process. The main purpose of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of communicative culture of schoolchildren, teaching practical mastery of a foreign language.

To date, the updating of the content of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan has set a main goal: to improve the pedagogical skills of teachers in the context of updating the educational program and the introduction of a system of criteria-based assessment.

It is known that English is among the most difficult subjects of the school course. Therefore, one of the main tasks is considered to instill interest, as well as increase motivation for the subject, the desire to awaken in students creative and intellectual forces.

Knowledge of English in the modern world is a kind of window into the world. Knowing this language of international communication, you can achieve your goals with the help of new opportunities.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for the practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity, as well as to enhance the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages.

With the mastery of any new technology begins a new pedagogical thinking of the teacher: clarity, structure, clarity of methodical language, the emergence of a reasonable standard in the methodology.

Using new pedagogical technologies in the classroom, you can make sure that the process of learning English can be viewed from a new point of view and to master the psychological mechanisms of personality formation, achieving better results.

In summary, to improve the efficiency of the educational process during English lessons e such educational technologies as game, project method, pictogram, crafting, group work, forms of dialogue, as well as multi-touch writing, taking into account the age characteristics of learners.

REFERENCES

1. Jamie Pickrell. Why One Should Learn listening Via The Internet <http://ezinearticles.com/?Why-One-Should-Learn-English-Via-The-Internet&id=5208379>
2. Selami Aydin. The Use of The listening strategies in ESL Learning <http://www.hltmag.co.uk/jan07/sart02.htm>
3. The Linux Information Project <http://www.linfo.org/internet.html>
4. Steffanie Zazulak. How the podcasts can help English language learners <https://www.english.com/blog/internet-can-help-english-language-learners>